

Raport statystyczny

Parametry okulistyczne MD i VFI

MD

MD

MD right (NTG, HTG)

group	Średnia	SD	Mediana	Min	Max	Ilość	Zmienna
HTG	-2.83	1.76	-1.81	-5.36	-0.51	10	MD.OP
NTG	-3.18	2.18	-3.01	-6.79	-0.17	15	MD.OP

Normality

Test Shapiro-Wilka dla MD.OP (grupa ")

- Statystyka W = 0.931
- p-value = 0.2857

Test Shapiro-Wilka dla MD.OP (grupa ")

- Statystyka W = 0.844
- p-value = 0.04923

Levene

```
leveneTest(MD.OP ~ group, data = filter(dane, group %in% c("NTG", "HTG")))
```

Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)

```
  Df F value Pr(>F)
group 1  0.4022 0.5322
     23
```

t test

```
t.test(MD.OP ~ group, data = filter(dane, group %in% c("NTG", "HTG")),
var.equal = TRUE)
```

Two Sample t-test

data: MD.OP by group

t = 0.4308, df = 23, p-value = 0.6706

alternative hypothesis: true difference in means between group HTG and group NTG is not equal to 0

95 percent confidence interval:

-1.354750 2.067417

```
sample estimates:
mean in group HTG mean in group NTG
      -2.827000      -3.183333
```

MD left

group	Średnia	SD	Mediana	Min	Max	Ilość	Zmienna
HTG	-3.04	1.44	-3.21	-5.24	-0.63	10	MD.OL
NTG	-3.71	2.07	-3.61	-6.97	-0.27	15	MD.OL

Normality

```
shapiro_test_U <- shapiro.test(dane$MD.OL[dane$group == "NTG"])
glue(" ##### Test Shapiro-Wilka dla MD.OL (grupa 'NTG')
- Statystyka W = {round(shapiro_test_U$statistic, 3)}
- p-value = {format.pval(shapiro_test_U$p.value, digits = 4, eps = 0.0001)}
")
```

```
##### Test Shapiro-Wilka dla MD.OL (grupa 'NTG')
- Statystyka W = 0.95
- p-value = 0.5169
```

```
shapiro_test_U <- shapiro.test(dane$MD.OL[dane$group == "HTG"])
glue(" ##### Test Shapiro-Wilka dla MD.OL (grupa 'HTG')
- Statystyka W = {round(shapiro_test_U$statistic, 3)}
- p-value = {format.pval(shapiro_test_U$p.value, digits = 4, eps = 0.0001)}
")
```

```
##### Test Shapiro-Wilka dla MD.OL (grupa 'HTG')
- Statystyka W = 0.948
- p-value = 0.6403
```

```
leveneTest(MD.OL ~ group, data = filter(dane, group %in% c("NTG", "HTG")))
```

Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)

```
      Df F value Pr(>F)
group 1  2.1586 0.1553
      23
```

```
t.test(MD.OL ~ group, data = filter(dane, group %in% c("NTG", "HTG")),
var.equal = TRUE)
```

Two Sample t-test

data: MD.OL by group

t = 0.89065, df = 23, p-value = 0.3823

alternative hypothesis: true difference in means between group HTG and group NTG is not equal to 0

95 percent confidence interval:

```
-0.8897019 2.2350352
sample estimates:
mean in group HTG mean in group NTG
      -3.038000      -3.710667
```

VFI

VFI left

group	Średnia	SD	Mediana	Min	Max	Ilość	Zmienna
HTG	94.30	3.13	95.50	89.00	98.00	10	VFI.OL
NTG	88.40	8.64	91.00	74.00	99.00	15	VFI.OL

normality

Test Shapiro-Wilka dla VFI.OL(grupa ”)

- Statystyka W = 0.879
- p-value = 0.04552

Test Shapiro-Wilka dla VFI.OL (grupa ”)

- Statystyka W = 0.908
- p-value = 0.2708

Levene

```
leveneTest(VFI.OL ~ group, data = filter(dane, group %in% c("NTG", "HTG")))
```

Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)

```
      Df F value Pr(>F)
group 1  4.3474 0.04836 *
      23
```

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Wilcoxon

```
wilcox.test(VFI.OL ~ group, data = filter(dane, group %in% c("NTG", "HTG")))
```

Wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction

data: VFI.OL by group

W = 106.5, p-value = 0.08419

alternative hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0

```
t.test(VFI.OL ~ group, data = filter(dane, group %in% c("NTG", "HTG")),
var.equal = TRUE)
```

Two Sample t-test

```
data: VFI.OL by group
t = 2.0585, df = 23, p-value = 0.05105
alternative hypothesis: true difference in means between group HTG and group
NTG is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 -0.02922793 11.82922793
sample estimates:
mean in group HTG mean in group NTG
          94.3          88.4
```

VFI right

group	Średnia	SD	Mediana	Min	Max	Ilość	Zmienna
HTG	94.60	3.81	97.00	88.00	98.00	10	VFI.OP
NTG	88.67	7.03	86.00	76.00	98.00	15	VFI.OP

Normality

Test Shapiro-Wilka dla VFI.OP (grupa ")

- Statystyka W = 0.916
- p-value = 0.1684

Test Shapiro-Wilka dla VFI.OP (grupa ")

- Statystyka W = 0.807
- p-value = 0.01783

Levene

```
leveneTest(VFI.OP~ group, data = filter(dane, group %in% c("NTG", "HTG")))
```

Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)

```
  Df F value Pr(>F)
group 1  2.4747 0.1294
      23
```

t test

```
t.test(VFI.OP~ group, data = filter(dane, group %in% c("NTG", "HTG")),
var.equal = TRUE)
```

Two Sample t-test

```
data: VFI.OP by group
t = 2.4315, df = 23, p-value = 0.02324
alternative hypothesis: true difference in means between group HTG and group
NTG is not equal to 0
```

```
95 percent confidence interval:
 0.8853894 10.9812773
sample estimates:
mean in group HTG mean in group NTG
 94.60000          88.66667
```

Correlacions

LEFT EYE

Shapiro-Wilk test

```
zmienne <- c("OL.av", "OL.S", "OL.I", "OL.T", "OL.N")

wyniki <- map_df(zmienne, function(zmienna) {
  x <- suppressWarnings(as.numeric(dane[[zmienna]]))
  x <- x[is.finite(x)]
  n <- length(x)

  if (n >= 3 && stats::sd(x) > 0) {
    test <- shapiro.test(x)
    tibble(
      zmienna = zmienna,
      n       = n,
      W       = round(unname(test$statistic), 3),
      p.value = signif(test$p.value, 4)
    )
  } else {
    tibble(
      zmienna = zmienna,
      n       = n,
      W       = NA_real_,
      p.value = NA_real_
    )
  }
})

print(wyniki)

# A tibble: 5 × 4
  zmienna      n      W p.value
  <chr>    <int> <dbl> <dbl>
1 OL.av      39 0.983 0.812
2 OL.S       39 0.979 0.668
3 OL.I       39 0.962 0.202
4 OL.T       39 0.973 0.447
5 OL.N       39 0.984 0.828
```

Shapiro-Wilk test in groups

```
zmienna <- c("OL.av", "OL.S", "OL.I", "OL.T", "OL.N")

wyniki <- zmienna %>%
  map_df(function(zmienna) {
    dane %>%
      select(group, all_of(zmienna)) %>%
      rename(wartosc = all_of(zmienna)) %>%
      filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG", "K")) %>%
      mutate(wartosc = as.numeric(wartosc)) %>%
      group_by(group) %>%
      summarise(
        n = sum(!is.na(wartosc)),
        test = if (n() >= 3) list(shapiro.test(wartosc)) else NA,
        .groups = "drop"
      ) %>%
      mutate(
        zmienna = zmienna,
        statistic = map_dbl(test, ~ if (is.list(.x)) .x$statistic else
NA_real_),
        p.value = map_dbl(test, ~ if (is.list(.x)) .x$p.value else NA_real_)
      ) %>%
      select(group, zmienna, n, statistic, p.value)
  })

print(wyniki)

# A tibble: 15 × 5
  group zmienna      n statistic p.value
  <chr> <chr>   <int>   <dbl>   <dbl>
1 HTG   OL.av     10     0.938  0.528
2 K     OL.av     14     0.976  0.945
3 NTG   OL.av     15     0.979  0.965
4 HTG   OL.S      10     0.940  0.550
5 K     OL.S      14     0.910  0.159
6 NTG   OL.S      15     0.974  0.908
7 HTG   OL.I      10     0.890  0.168
8 K     OL.I      14     0.984  0.992
9 NTG   OL.I      15     0.956  0.626
10 HTG  OL.T      10     0.944  0.601
11 K    OL.T      14     0.966  0.815
12 NTG  OL.T      15     0.899  0.0919
13 HTG  OL.N      10     0.947  0.636
14 K    OL.N      14     0.879  0.0564
15 NTG  OL.N      15     0.968  0.833

dane_long <- dane %>%
  dplyr::filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG", "K")) %>%
  mutate(group = dplyr::recode(as.character(group), "K" = "C")) %>%
  dplyr::select(group, LGN_lh, OL.av, OL.S, OL.I, OL.T, OL.N) %>%
```

```

pivot_longer(cols = starts_with("OL."),
             names_to = "zmienna",
             values_to = "OL_wartosc") %>%
mutate(
  OL_wartosc = as.numeric(OL_wartosc)
)

p <- ggplot(dane_long, aes(x = OL_wartosc, y = LGN_lh, color = group)) +
  geom_point(alpha = 0.7, size = 2) +
  facet_wrap(~ zmienna, scales = "free", strip.position = "bottom") + #
osobna skala X i Y
  labs(title = "",
       x = NULL,
       y = "LGN LEFT",
       color = "Groups") +
  scale_x_continuous(n.breaks = 4) +
  scale_y_continuous(n.breaks = 5) +
  theme_classic(base_size = 13) +
  theme(
    strip.background = element_blank(),
    strip.placement = "outside",
    strip.text = element_text(face = "bold"),
    panel.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA),
    plot.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA)
  )
p

```



```
#ggsave("LGN_lh_vs_OL_osobne_Y.png", plot = p, width = 10, height = 6, dpi = 300)
```

Pearson Corr

```
zmienne_OL <- c("OL.av", "OL.S", "OL.I", "OL.T", "OL.N")

wyniki_pearson_all <- map_dfr(zmienne_OL, function(zmienna) {
  x <- suppressWarnings(as.numeric(dane$LGN_lh))
  y <- suppressWarnings(as.numeric(dane[[zmienna]]))
  ok <- is.finite(x) & is.finite(y)
  x <- x[ok]; y <- y[ok]
  n <- length(x)

  if (n >= 3 && stats::var(x) > 0 && stats::var(y) > 0) {
    test <- cor.test(x, y, method = "pearson", conf.level = 0.95)
    tibble::tibble(
      zmienna      = zmienna,
      r            = round(unname(test$estimate), 3),
      `95% CI low` = round(test$conf.int[1], 3),
      `95% CI high` = round(test$conf.int[2], 3),
      p.value      = ifelse(test$p.value < 1e-4, "<0.0001",
round(test$p.value, 4)),
      n            = n
    )
  }
})
```

```

)
} else {
  tibble::tibble(
    zmienna = zmienna, r = NA_real_,
    `95% CI low` = NA_real_, `95% CI high` = NA_real_,
    p.value = NA_real_, n = n
  )
}
})

```

```
print(wyniki_pearson_all)
```

```
# A tibble: 5 × 6
  zmienna      r `95% CI low` `95% CI high` p.value      n
  <chr>    <dbl>      <dbl>      <dbl>    <dbl> <int>
1 OL.av    0.537        0.258        0.734  0.0006     37
2 OL.S     0.591        0.331        0.768  0.0001     37
3 OL.I     0.435        0.129        0.665  0.0071     37
4 OL.T     0.26         -0.07        0.539  0.120      37
5 OL.N     0.296       -0.031        0.566  0.0749     37
```

Pearson Corr in groups

```

zmienne_OL <- c("OL.av", "OL.S", "OL.I", "OL.T", "OL.N")
grupy <- c("NTG", "HTG", "K")

wyniki_pearson <- expand.grid(zmienna = zmienne_OL, grupa = grupy,
stringsAsFactors = FALSE) %>%
  pmap_dfr(function(zmienna, grupa) {

    podzbior <- dane %>%
      filter(group == grupa) %>%
      dplyr::select(LGN_lh, zmienna = dplyr::all_of(zmienna)) %>%
      mutate(across(everything(), as.numeric)) %>%
      filter(is.finite(LGN_lh) & is.finite(zmienna))

    n <- nrow(podzbior)

    if (n >= 3 && stats::var(podzbior$LGN_lh) > 0 &&
stats::var(podzbior$zmienna) > 0) {
      test <- cor.test(podzbior$LGN_lh, podzbior$zmienna,
        method = "pearson", conf.level = 0.95)

      tibble::tibble(
        grupa = grupa,
        zmienna = zmienna,
        r = round(unnamed(test$estimate), 3),
        `95% CI low` = round(test$conf.int[1], 3),
        `95% CI high` = round(test$conf.int[2], 3),
        p.value = ifelse(test$p.value < 0.0001, "<0.0001",

```

```

round(test$p.value, 4)),
  n = n
)
} else {
  tibble::tibble(grupa = grupa, zmienna = zmienna,
                 r = NA_real_, `95% CI low` = NA_real_, `95% CI high` =
NA_real_,
                 p.value = NA_real_, n = n)
}
})

```

```
print(wyniki_pearson)
```

```
# A tibble: 15 × 7
```

	grupa	zmienna	r	`95% CI low`	`95% CI high`	p.value	n
	<chr>	<chr>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<int>
1	NTG	OL.av	0.151	-0.436	0.648	0.622	13
2	NTG	OL.S	0.495	-0.076	0.822	0.0852	13
3	NTG	OL.I	-0.144	-0.644	0.442	0.638	13
4	NTG	OL.T	-0.051	-0.586	0.514	0.868	13
5	NTG	OL.N	0.187	-0.406	0.669	0.542	13
6	HTG	OL.av	0.595	-0.056	0.891	0.0698	10
7	HTG	OL.S	0.504	-0.184	0.861	0.137	10
8	HTG	OL.I	0.542	-0.133	0.874	0.105	10
9	HTG	OL.T	0.334	-0.374	0.796	0.345	10
10	HTG	OL.N	0.57	-0.093	0.883	0.0854	10
11	K	OL.av	0.259	-0.315	0.694	0.371	14
12	K	OL.S	0.09	-0.462	0.593	0.759	14
13	K	OL.I	0.243	-0.33	0.685	0.402	14
14	K	OL.T	0.31	-0.264	0.722	0.281	14
15	K	OL.N	-0.049	-0.565	0.494	0.867	14

RIGHT EYE

Shapiro-Wilk

```
zmienne <- c("OP.av", "OP.S", "OP.I", "OP.T", "OP.N")
```

```

wyniki <- map_df(zmienne, function(zmienna) {
  x <- suppressWarnings(as.numeric(dane[[zmienna]]))
  x <- x[is.finite(x)]
  n <- length(x)

  if (n >= 3 && stats::sd(x) > 0) {
    test <- shapiro.test(x)
    tibble(
      zmienna = zmienna,
      n = n,
      W = round(unname(test$statistic), 3),
      p.value = signif(test$p.value, 4)
    )
  }
})

```

```

    )
  } else {
    tibble(
      zmienna = zmienna,
      n       = n,
      W       = NA_real_,
      p.value = NA_real_
    )
  }
})

```

```
print(wyniki)
```

```

# A tibble: 5 × 4
  zmienna      n      W p.value
  <chr>   <int> <dbl> <dbl>
1 OP.av     39 0.967 0.302
2 OP.S     39 0.952 0.0995
3 OP.I     39 0.972 0.433
4 OP.T     39 0.869 0.000327
5 OP.N     39 0.977 0.593

```

Shapiro-Wilk in groups

```
zmienne <- c("OP.av", "OP.S", "OP.I", "OP.T", "OP.N")
```

```

wyniki <- zmienne %>%
  map_df(function(zmienna) {
    dane %>%
      select(group, all_of(zmienna)) %>%
      rename(wartosc = all_of(zmienna)) %>%
      filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG", "K")) %>%
      mutate(wartosc = as.numeric(wartosc)) %>% # KONWERSJA TYPÓW
      group_by(group) %>%
      summarise(
        n = sum(!is.na(wartosc)),
        test = if (n() >= 3) list(shapiro.test(wartosc)) else NA,
        .groups = "drop"
      ) %>%
      mutate(
        zmienna = zmienna,
        statistic = map_dbl(test, ~ if (is.list(.x)) .x$statistic else
NA_real_),
        p.value = map_dbl(test, ~ if (is.list(.x)) .x$p.value else NA_real_)
      ) %>%
      select(group, zmienna, n, statistic, p.value)
  })

```

```
print(wyniki)
```

```
# A tibble: 15 × 5
  group zmienna      n statistic p.value
  <chr> <chr>   <int>   <dbl>   <dbl>
1 HTG   OP.av     10     0.850 0.0579
2 K     OP.av     14     0.980 0.976
3 NTG   OP.av     15     0.943 0.421
4 HTG   OP.S      10     0.920 0.355
5 K     OP.S      14     0.948 0.528
6 NTG   OP.S      15     0.932 0.295
7 HTG   OP.I      10     0.929 0.434
8 K     OP.I      14     0.958 0.685
9 NTG   OP.I      15     0.957 0.646
10 HTG  OP.T      10     0.742 0.00284
11 K    OP.T      14     0.950 0.556
12 NTG  OP.T      15     0.898 0.0895
13 HTG  OP.N      10     0.937 0.517
14 K    OP.N      14     0.974 0.926
15 NTG  OP.N      15     0.904 0.110
```

```
dane_long <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG", "K")) %>%
  mutate(group = dplyr::recode(as.character(group), "K" = "C")) %>%
  dplyr::select(group, LGN_rh, OP.av, OP.S, OP.I, OP.T, OP.N) %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = starts_with("OP."),
               names_to = "zmienna",
               values_to = "OP_wartosc") %>%
  mutate(OP_wartosc = as.numeric(OP_wartosc)) %>%
  filter(!(zmienna == "OP.T" & OP_wartosc > 120))
```

```
p <- ggplot(dane_long, aes(x = OP_wartosc, y = LGN_rh, color = group)) +
  geom_point(alpha = 0.7, size = 2) +
  facet_wrap(~ zmienna, scales = "free", strip.position = "bottom") +
  labs(title = "",
        x = NULL,
        y = "LGN RIGHT",
        color = "Groups") +
  scale_x_continuous(n.breaks = 4) +
  scale_y_continuous(n.breaks = 5) +
  theme_classic(base_size = 13) +
  theme(
    strip.background = element_blank(),
    strip.placement = "outside",
    strip.text = element_text(face = "bold"),
    panel.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA),
    plot.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = NA)
  )
```

p


```
#ggsave("LGN_rh_vs_OP_osobne_Y.png", plot = p, width = 10, height = 6, dpi = 300)
```

Pearson Corr

```
zmienne_OP <- c("OP.av", "OP.S", "OP.I", "OP.T", "OP.N")

wyniki_pearson_all <- map_dfr(zmienne_OP, function(zmienna) {
  x <- suppressWarnings(as.numeric(dane$LGN_rh))
  y <- suppressWarnings(as.numeric(dane[[zmienna]]))
  ok <- is.finite(x) & is.finite(y)
  x <- x[ok]; y <- y[ok]
  n <- length(x)

  if (n >= 3 && stats::var(x) > 0 && stats::var(y) > 0) {
    test <- cor.test(x, y, method = "pearson", conf.level = 0.95)
    tibble::tibble(
      zmienna      = zmienna,
      r            = round(unname(test$estimate), 3),
      `95% CI low` = round(test$conf.int[1], 3),
      `95% CI high` = round(test$conf.int[2], 3),
      p.value      = ifelse(test$p.value < 1e-4, "<0.0001",
round(test$p.value, 4)),
      n            = n
    )
  }
})
```

```

)
} else {
  tibble::tibble(
    zmienna = zmienna, r = NA_real_,
    `95% CI low` = NA_real_, `95% CI high` = NA_real_,
    p.value = NA_real_, n = n
  )
}
})

```

```
print(wyniki_pearson_all)
```

```
# A tibble: 5 × 6
  zmienna      r `95% CI low` `95% CI high` p.value      n
  <chr>      <dbl>      <dbl>         <dbl>    <dbl> <int>
1 OP.av      0.196      -0.136         0.489    0.244    37
2 OP.S       0.209      -0.124         0.499    0.215    37
3 OP.I       0.243      -0.088         0.526    0.147    37
4 OP.T       0.121      -0.211         0.428    0.476    37
5 OP.N      -0.107      -0.416         0.225    0.529    37
```

Pearson Corr in groups

```

zmienne_OP <- c("OP.av", "OP.S", "OP.I", "OP.T", "OP.N")
grupy <- c("NTG", "HTG", "K")

wyniki_pearson <- expand.grid(zmienna = zmienne_OP, grupa = grupy,
stringsAsFactors = FALSE) %>%
  pmap_dfr(function(zmienna, grupa) {

    podzbior <- dane %>%
      filter(group == grupa) %>%
      dplyr::select(LGN_rh, zmienna = dplyr::all_of(zmienna)) %>%
      mutate(across(everything(), as.numeric)) %>%
      filter(is.finite(LGN_rh) & is.finite(zmienna))

    n <- nrow(podzbior)

    if (n >= 3 && stats::var(podzbior$LGN_rh) > 0 &&
stats::var(podzbior$zmienna) > 0) {
      test <- cor.test(podzbior$LGN_rh, podzbior$zmienna,
method = "pearson", conf.level = 0.95)

      tibble::tibble(
        grupa = grupa,
        zmienna = zmienna,
        r = round(unnamed(test$estimate), 3),
        `95% CI low` = round(test$conf.int[1], 3),
        `95% CI high` = round(test$conf.int[2], 3),
        p.value = ifelse(test$p.value < 0.0001, "<0.0001",

```

```

round(test$p.value, 4)),
  n = n
)
} else {
  tibble::tibble(grupa = grupa, zmienna = zmienna,
    r = NA_real_, `95% CI low` = NA_real_, `95% CI high` =
NA_real_,
    p.value = NA_real_, n = n)
}
})

```

```
print(wyniki_pearson)
```

```
# A tibble: 15 × 7
```

	grupa	zmienna	r	`95% CI low`	`95% CI high`	p.value	n
	<chr>	<chr>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<int>
1	NTG	OP.av	0.32	-0.281	0.74	0.287	13
2	NTG	OP.S	0.379	-0.218	0.769	0.202	13
3	NTG	OP.I	0.067	-0.502	0.596	0.828	13
4	NTG	OP.T	0.341	-0.258	0.751	0.254	13
5	NTG	OP.N	-0.044	-0.581	0.519	0.886	13
6	HTG	OP.av	-0.26	-0.764	0.442	0.469	10
7	HTG	OP.S	-0.11	-0.692	0.558	0.762	10
8	HTG	OP.I	-0.038	-0.652	0.606	0.917	10
9	HTG	OP.T	-0.361	-0.807	0.348	0.305	10
10	HTG	OP.N	-0.387	-0.817	0.321	0.269	10
11	K	OP.av	-0.103	-0.601	0.452	0.726	14
12	K	OP.S	-0.211	-0.667	0.359	0.468	14
13	K	OP.I	-0.027	-0.55	0.511	0.927	14
14	K	OP.T	0.136	-0.426	0.621	0.644	14
15	K	OP.N	-0.065	-0.576	0.482	0.826	14